

D4.2 Report from supportive start-up meeting, 1st round

WP4 Joint Integrative Projects

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: Sciansano

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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Leader	SVA
Other contributors	Sciensano
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Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

Report from supportive start-up meeting for projects funded in the first round of the One Health European Joint Programme

Background

Task 4.2 of WP4 Joint Integrative Projects (JIP) deals with support to, and supervision of, JIPs. As part of the support, activities are in place to ensure the successful launch of new projects. This activity is in full alignment with similar needs in WP3.

One such supportive activity was the arrangement of a pre-kick-off meeting (P-KOM) for project leaders, deputy project leader or their replacements. The P-KOM took place in Brussels, at the Eurostation building of the Federal Public Service (Ministry) of Public Health, on 15 December 2017, i.e. before the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP) had officially started. Consequently, the costs incurred were incurred by the institutes themselves.

The purpose of the pre-kick-off meeting was to inform JRP and JIP representatives on practical issues related to the research and integrative projects, i.e. guidelines, scientific and financial reporting, ethical issues, the use of a collaborative platform and data management. Another objective was to allow project leaders to network, and to increase their knowledge about background on the OHEJP.

Invitation

An invitation to the meeting was sent out on 3 October 2017 with the following information:

“The Programme Management Team agreed last month that WP3 and WP4 would organise a pre-kick-off meeting for the JRP and JIP coordinators. The aim of this is to provide you with practical information on the periodic and final reporting of the projects, intermediate and final evaluations and on the impact of JRP and JIP on the overall objectives of the One Health EJP.

The meeting will take place on Friday December 15th in Brussels, at the Eurostation building of the Federal Public Service (Ministry) of Public Health, Place Victor Horta 40, 1060 Brussels, room Permeke B. It would be useful if per JRP and JIP one or two persons attend the meeting of which one should be project coordinator or deputy coordinator. Also, members of the Programme Management Team (PMT) and support team will be present. As this meeting is organised before the start of the OneHealth EJP, no reimbursement of travel costs is possible. A sandwich lunch and soft drinks will be offered.”

Agenda

The agenda included the following items:

- 10.00-10.30: Welcome and introduction of attendees
- 10.30-11.30: General introduction One Health EJP (André Jestin)
 - Overview of the EJP and WP3 and 4 (Hein Imberechts & Ann Lindberg)
 - Overview of projects in the domain/themes matrix (Hein Imberechts)
- 11.30-12.15: Procedures WP3 and 4
 - Reporting procedures, deadlines (Hein Imberechts)
 - Financial issues (Arnaud Callegari)
- 12.15-12.30: Ethics (Hein Imberechts)
- 13.15-13.45: Collaborative platform and introduction to data management plan (Ann Lindberg)
- 13.45-15.30: Elevator pitch/short introduction of projects (5 slides max, 5 minutes)
ORION, COHESIVE, IMPART, ARDIG, RADAR, MADVIR, TOXDetect, NOVA, ListAdapt, METASTAVA, AirSample, MoMIR PPC, MEDVETKLEBS
- 15.30-16.00: Next steps, questions & feedback on the provided information
- 16.00: End of meeting

Action points

The following actions and clarifications were noted at the meeting, to be followed up by WP3 and WP4 leaders, as well as the Support Team (ST).

1. Find unique name for the EJP Project Leaders (PL) group (All, PMT).
2. Deputy Project Leaders (DPL) should be identified (WP3 and WP4 leaders will always have the PL as primary contact point, but appointed DPLs are of value as backup) (see below, document with brief description of projects) (For PLs that do not yet have a DPL).
3. Distribute list with SSB members to PLs (ST).
4. Project extensions without extra budget are possible, in principle, but reporting must be within the time frame of the EJP, i.e. not later than 31 December 2022.
5. Budget adjustments are possible, the process for validation needs to be clarified (ST)
6. Project management platform:
 - a. Can the OHEJP pay for it (is this an eligible cost)? (PMT). WP3 and 4 leaders would like to see such a platform being used by all projects, in case it is paid for by the OHEJP centrally.
 - b. There was a concern expressed that some institutions may not allow platforms that give access to many external partners.

7. Are there project management tools that can be used to share big data? (note: ORION PL (matthias.filter@bfr.bund.de) will use a so called Virtual Research Environment developed by another EU funded project).
8. Communication: University of Surrey will start activities in this field but are currently recruiting. Developments include web page with access to platform for projects where documents can be shared.
9. Communication via video conference: Several institutes mention that Skype or other freeware is not allowed. With respect to payment, see item 6 above.
10. There is an interest to share more information on all the JRP and JIP with e.g. ECDC, including details of WPs and contact details of WP leaders. A document with an overview (summaries from project proposals) will be sent out, to be completed with contact details of the Deputy Project Leader and WP leader (Responsibility: WP3). This document can later be used for communication purposes, or information on web page or in leaflets (Responsibility: WP6).

A fruitful impact of the meeting was that, following the pitch presentations, several PL showed the intention to make contact with others and look for collaboration / reduce redundancy.

Participants

Name	Partner	Role / project name
André Jestin	Anses	OHEJP WP1 leader
Arjen van de Giessen	RIVM	OHEJP WP2 leader
Hein Imberechts	CODA-CERVA	OHEJP WP3 leader
Hendrik-Jan Roest	WBVR	OHEJP WP3 deputy leader
Ann Lindberg	SVA	OHEJP WP4 leader
Valérie de Waele	CODA-CERVA	OHEJP WP4 task lead DMP
Roberto La Ragione	University of Surrey	OHEJP WP6 leader
Camille Pestre	Anses	OHEJP Support Team
Arnaud Callegari (on phone)	Anses	OHEJP Support Team
Anna Nordenfelt	SVA	Financial officer, SVA
Muna Anjum	APHA	ARDIG
Kitty Maassen	RIVM	COHESIVE
Kees Veldman	WBVR	IMPART
Laurent Guillier	Anses	LISTADAPT
Anders Fomsgaard	SSI	MADVIR
Maiken Rosenstjerne	SSI	MADVIR
Sylvain Brisse	Institut Pasteur	MedVetKlebs
Steven van Borm	CODA-CERVA	METASTAVA
Antonio Rodriguez-Bertos	VISAVET-UCM	MoMIR PPC
Philippe Velge	INRA	MoMIR PPC
Steen Ethelberg	SSI	NOVA
Jenny Frössling	SVA	NOVA

Participants, cont'd.

Name	Partner	Role / project
Matthias Filter	BfR	ORION
Idesbald Boone	BfR	ORION
Fernanda Dórea	SVA	ORION
Eelco Franz	RIVM	RADAR
Mirjana Andjelkovic	WIV-ISP	ToxDetect
Ed van Klink	WBVR	OHEJP WP3 deputy leader secretary
Soizic Sergeant	Institut Pasteur	Grant officer, IP

Presentations

The presentations given by WP3 and WP4 leaders, as well as the project pitch presentations are provided in Appendix 1.

EJP: One Health Zoonoses – Emerging Threats

EU Project 773830

**Procedures for Joint Research (WP3) and
Integrative (WP4) Projects**

**Hein Imberechts, Hendrik-Jan Roest,
Ann Lindberg and Manuela Caniça**

December 15th, 2017: pre-kick-off meeting, Brussels BE

Agenda

- Aim of the meeting
- General introduction of OneHealth EJP
- Procedures for WP3 and WP4
- Annual Scientific Meetings
- Ethics
- Collaborative platform
- Data management plan
- Presentation of the projects (JRP and JIP)
- Next steps & questions

Aim of the meeting

- Aim = to give support to the Project Leaders
 - Guidance on reporting, ethics issues, use of a collaborative platform and data management
 - However, some practical arrangements are not clear yet
 - In addition, you may have questions that Support Team or PMT will clarify later

General introduction of OH EJP

Mission & Strategy

The EJP aims to create a sustainable European network of medical, veterinary and public health institutes aiming to match the EU's international policy to future health threats such as zoonotic infections and antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats. This will be done by **integration and alignment** of work processes and infrastructures of joint priority and through joint programming of research agendas.

**TO GET BETTER
PREPARED!**

Characteristics of EJPs

- Based on EU policy objectives and regulations outside R&I policy
- The aim is to bring together national public entities, with R&I activities as part of their mission while R&I not being necessarily the core function
 - Contribute scientifically to policy implementation
- In contrast to the ERA-NET scheme, main actors are not R&I funding agencies
 - Rather, public entities with policy-driven R&I
 - Complement, not duplicate
- Organisations with mandates, responsibilities; often based on existing network

One Health EJP Consortium

- "Me+Ve" partnership
- Institutes and agencies with reference functions and applied, policy-driven research on zoonotic transmissible hazards (pathogens, AMR)
- Societal responsibility for prevention, surveillance and preparedness to respond
- National agencies, represented in the networks set up by the respective EU agencies (ECDC and EFSA)

EJP : 41 partners from 19 countries

Governance

Two types of projects

- Research Projects
 - Typical scientific studies addressing specific R&I objectives
 - May also contain long term integrative actions
- Integrative Projects
 - Aim at developing common protocols, databases or infrastructure that support collaborative processes
 - E.g. platforms for uploading, sharing and analysing sequence data, experimental facilities or risk assessment structures
 - The deliverables should become integrated into the work processes of project partners; impact-oriented and sustainable outcome

Development of the strategic agenda

THEMES	DOMAINES		
	Foodborne zoonoses (FBZ)	Antimicrobial resistance (AMR)	Emerging threats (ET)
Analytical methods			
Host-microbe interaction			
Epidemiology			
Risk assessment			
Intervention			

Narrowing down to priority topics

Detailed topic descriptions

Proposal

First call for projects
(11 JRPs, 2 JIPs)

Research projects first call

	DOMAINES		
THEMES	Food Borne Zoonoses (FBZ)	AntiMicrobial resistance (AMR)	Emerging threats (ET)
Analytical methods	METASTAVA	IMPART	MAD-VIR
	LISTADAPT		TOX-Detect
Host-microbe interaction			
Epidemiology	NOVA	ARDIG	
	MedVetKlebs		
Risk assessment		RaDAR	
Intervention	AIR-SAMPLE		
	MoMIR-PPC		

Integrative projects first call

Procedures for WP3 and WP4

Start of JRP & JIP

- JRP and JIP from first call:
 - Start January 2018
 - Will last 2 or 3 years

Reporting on Projects

- Newly started projects, by means of online questionnaire in Jan-Feb 2018
 - Quick and useful feedback, will be briefed to SSB by mail
- First and/or second year report
 - After 12 months; to be submitted in Jan 2019, 2020
 - Will be discussed by next SSB in February
 - In case of poor output (criteria), project may be stopped
- First call projects may request for extension
 - Submission in June 2019 and June 2020
 - Evaluation by SSB in September (specific criteria)
- Final project report one month after project end
 - Will be evaluated by external experts
 - Reports will be discussed by SSB

Intermediate reports

- Reports should contain (paragraphs in template)
 - Scientific results and progress
 - Compliance with needs stakeholders ECDC, EFSA
 - One Health, public health benefits
 - Integrative aspects and actions, harmonization efforts, engagement of partners in the long term
 - (Financial reporting will be covered later)

Intermediate reports

- Reports will be discussed by SSB
 - Scientific progress will be presented in ASM, not in SSB (no scientific presentations in SSB)
 - WP3/4 may invite Project Leaders based on achievements and strategic added value
 - WP3/4 aim to stay in contact with JRP and JIP, formally and informally
 - Coordinators may propose to be heard by SSB

Intermediate reports

- WP3/4 a particular project
 - Interaction with Project Coordinators is essential
 - Criteria for eventual cessation
 - Poor management
 - Insufficient (scientific) progress
 - Insufficient integration activities
 - Other ?
 - SSB decides

Request for extension

- Only possible for 1st call projects
 - 2 year projects: 1 to max 6 months extension
 - 3 year projects: idem
- Aim: to finalise valuable projects under the best conditions
 - Results are promising, and extra time can improve the value of the output further
 - Valuable integration possibilities are present
 - ...

Request for extension

- Applies equally to JIP and JRP
 - Need for extra time and limited extra budget to finish up the work
 - Requests should be submitted in June 2019 and June 2020; will be evaluated by SSB only, without external evaluation
 - Opportunity to enhance integration
 - Not acceptable: to explore new scientific ideas (which would be a new project)
- If a project is extended, the reporting will be adapted

Final project report

- Final report: two months after end date
- These reports will be evaluated by external evaluators
 - External evaluation reports must be available after 3 to 4 months
 - Will be discussed by SSB in September that year
- The final reports and external evaluation reports will be discussed with ESAB
 - How? Combined per domain? (tbd)
- These will serve as inputs to WP7, sustainability

Financial procedures

By the Support Team:
Arnaud Callegari
Camille Pestre

1. EJP budget setup (2)

2 kinds of budget matrices:

1. Per Partner and per Activity and per specific year (Y1-Y2-Y3-Y4-Y5) or for all years (Yall)

Example:

One Health
P01_Anses_budget

One Health
I_P01_Anses_budg

2. Per activity and per Partner and per specific year (Y1-Y2-Y3-Y4-Y5) or for all years (Yall)

Example:

One Health
JIP01_ORION_budg

One Health
I_JIP01_ORION_bu

2. JRP/JIP Budgeting (1)

H2020 standard project: Annex 1 workplan for entire project duration

H2020 EJP: Annex 1 + Annex 7: Annual workplan

Annual planification = annual budget set up

All JRPs and JIPs were asked to provide annual workplans and annual budgets

Total JRP/JIP budget = budget Y1 + budget Y2 (+ budget Y3)

2. JRP/JIP Budgeting (2)

Each Project Year:

A yearly budget is established for each JRP/JIP and sent out to each Project Leader.

Example (double click to open)
Y1-JIP01-ORION

Possibility to carry forward unspent budget Yn-1 into budget Yn upon request and justification (conditions and procedure still to set up).

2. JRP/JIP Budgetting (2)

In course of the year:

Budget adjustments are allowed upon request

	Cost item 1	Cost item 2	Cost item x
Partner 1			
Partner 2			
Partner y			

Between cost items in a same partner
Between partners for a same cost item
Between partners and cost items

Procedure to come under the form of

1. Request from Project Leader explaining the reason of the need for budget adjustment and amounts, cost items and partners impacted (using budget adjustment request form) available
2. Validation by the SSB members (institute reps) of the impacted partners
3. Processing by the Support Team
4. Updated budgets sent to Project Leader and impacted Partners

3. Reporting

Annual reports:

Scientific reports to be sent by Project Leaders to WP3/WP4 Leaders

Financial reports prepared at the Partner level, NOT at the project level.

i.e. each **beneficiary** reports to the Support Team for all activities it is involved in.

Annual Scientific Meetings

Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM)

- Essential part of One Health EJP:
 1. Dissemination of scientific results (JRPs, JIPs, PhD projects)
 - » → ANNUAL SCIENTIFIC REPORTING !
 2. To facilitate integration between
 - Different projects within OH EJP
 - Between themes and domains of OH EJP
 - Med – Vet – Food – Environment domain scientists
 - Young – Senior researchers
 3. Educational platform to present results
 4. Highlight specific themes, topics

ASM cont.

- Via, for example:
 - Posters
 - Presentations
 - Pitches
 - Videos
 - Workshops
 - Debate sessions
 -

ASM cont.

- In conjunction with ASM:
 - WP4 arranges thematic cross-domain integrative meetings, i.e. workshops/seminars around a specific cross-domain theme can be planned.
 - The specific topic for such meetings will be decided with theme experts
- Four meetings are planned: in April 2019, 2020, 2021 and 2022

Ethics issues

Ethics

- Concerning experiments, data, databases, protection of private life ...
- Tasks
 - Evaluate and report on new to start projects in 2018 and 2020 (based on your self-assessments); recommendations will be drawn
 - January 2018 and January 2020
 - Evaluate and yearly report on follow up of recommendations
 - You will report each year in December, referring to the recommendations mentioned in the January report
 - Ethics advisors report on that the following January

Ethics issues

- Two ethics advisors will be appointed
 - Not related to the OneHealth EJP beneficiaries
 - Terms of reference on ethics issues
 - Procedure
- Probable names
 - Kate Millar, University of Nottingham UK
 - François Hirsch, Inserm FR

Collaborative Platform

Project management platform inventory

#	Name of platform	web address	origin	freeof charge (Y/N)	usable at program and JIP/JRP level (Y/N)	user friendly 1 (poor)-5(very)	easy structure 1 (poor)-5(very)	why do you like it
1	Confluence	https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/fpfis/wikis#all-updates	EU	N	y	4-5	4	nice user interface
2	Virtual Research Environments	https://www.d4science.org	CNR (IT)	could be	Y	4	4	it also provide computational resources, e.g. cloud computing with R-Studio. Has been developed under EU funding. Hosted by Italian research institute.
3	Open Science Framework	https://osf.io						
4	Sharefile							includes a version back up system, focuses on the secure sharing of files
5	ALFRESCO (ANSES)							
6	office 365		microsoft	N	project Y; program ?	2	?	not suitable for us

1. Confluence

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=09CuRQoJzB8&list=PLaD4FvsFdarRn_gi46OIHZq9jPf0Pb43b9

The screenshot shows a video player interface for a Confluence welcome message. At the top, there are three navigation links: "Welcome", "Upload your photo", and "Find content". The main text reads "Hi Hendrik-Jan ROEST, welcome to Confluence!" followed by the instruction "Sit back, relax, and let us show you the basics." Below this text is a row of five document icons: a document with a green square, a document with a blue square, a document with a play button (the current video), a document with a green grid, and a document with a red square. At the bottom of the video player, there is a progress bar with a red line, a volume icon, and a timestamp "1:11 / 1:11". To the right of the progress bar are icons for a list, settings, and a full-screen button. A blue "Continue" button is located at the bottom right of the video player.

2. Virtual Research Environments

- <https://www.d4science.org>

The screenshot shows the D4Science.org website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for Home, About Us, Supported projects, Catalogue, Services, and Contact Us. The main heading is "Infrastructure Capacity". Below this, there is a paragraph describing D4Science as a Hybrid Data Infrastructure connecting +3900 scientists in 44 countries, integrating +50 heterogeneous data providers, executing +42,000 models & algorithms/month, providing access to over a billion quality records in repositories worldwide, with 99,7% service availability. It also mentions that D4Science hosts +95 Virtual Research Environments to serve the biological, ecological, environmental, and statistical communities world-wide. To the right of the text is a colorful globe icon made of small squares. Below the main text is a "Learn More" button with a play icon. At the bottom, there are three columns of information: "Infrastructure Capacity" (Access to a broad range of computational, storage and international data resources.), "Exploitation Models" (Three simple exploitation models to meet your needs), and "Data Catalogue" (Data discovery, accessing, analysis, and transformation in standard format.). Below these are two more sections: "Experiencing" (D4Science offers a number of services and virtual research environments for users willing to acquire concrete understanding of the major features and capabilities.) and "Empowering" (D4Science is supporting the operation of a large set of diverse Initiatives, Communities of Practice, and Projects by offering VREs and Services.).

D4SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE Home About Us Supported projects Catalogue Services Contact Us

D4Science.org is an organisation offering a **Hybrid Data Infrastructure** service and a number of **Virtual Research Environments**

Infrastructure Capacity

D4Science is a Hybrid Data Infrastructure connecting **+3900 scientists in 44 countries**, integrating **+50 heterogeneous data providers**, executing **+42,000 models & algorithms/month**; providing access to over a **billion quality records** in repositories worldwide, with **99,7% service availability**.

D4Science hosts **+95 Virtual Research Environments** to serve the biological, ecological, environmental, and statistical communities world-wide.

Learn More

Infrastructure Capacity

Access to a broad range of computational, storage and international data resources.

Exploitation Models

Three simple exploitation models to meet your needs

Data Catalogue

Data discovery, accessing, analysis, and transformation in standard format.

Experiencing

D4Science offers a number of services and virtual research environments for users willing to acquire concrete understanding of the major features and capabilities.

Empowering

D4Science is supporting the operation of a large set of diverse Initiatives, Communities of Practice, and Projects by offering VREs and Services.

3. Open Science Framework

- <https://osf.io/>

The image shows a screenshot of the Open Science Framework (OSF) website. The top navigation bar includes the OSFHOME logo, a search bar, and links for Support, Donate, Sign Up, and Sign In. The main heading reads "Open Science Framework" with the tagline "A scholarly commons to connect the entire research cycle". Below this is a graphic of a network of white and blue nodes. A white banner with the text "FREE AND OPEN SOURCE. START NOW." is positioned above a registration form. The form contains fields for Full Name, Contact Email, Confirm Email, and Password (Must be 8 to 255 characters), followed by a "Sign up free" button. A disclaimer states: "By clicking 'Sign up free', you agree to our Terms and that you have read our Privacy Policy, including our information on Cookie Use." In the bottom left, a smaller screenshot of a project page is shown, featuring a "Projects" table with columns for Name, Contributors, and a status column. A large orange play button icon is overlaid on the project page screenshot.

4. Sharefile

- <https://www.sharefile.com>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fWL2SbJr5d8>

The screenshot shows the Citrix ShareFile Support page. At the top, there is a Citrix logo and navigation links for Support, Sign In, and More from Citrix. Below this is a ShareFile logo and a navigation menu with links for Features, Pricing, Industries, Enterprise, Virtual Data Room, Resources, and a Try Free button. The main heading is "SHAREFILE SUPPORT" followed by the text "Real people. Real answers. Real quick. Welcome to ShareFile Support." and "Our mission is to raise the bar for support in the tech industry. We're on your team. How can we help you?". Below this are six icons representing different support topics: GETTING STARTED, WEB APPLICATION, OUTLOOK PLUGIN, SYNC, ENTERPRISE, and MASTER CLASS WEBINARS. A search bar is present with the text "More ways to get help — fast." and "Type your question here". At the bottom, there are four columns of text: "Ask the community.", "Send us your question.", "Customer adoption training.", and "Check system status.", each with a brief description of the service.

citrix 1 919 745 6111 Support Sign In More from Citrix

S ShareFile Features Pricing Industries Enterprise Virtual Data Room Resources **Try Free**

SHAREFILE SUPPORT

Real people. Real answers. Real quick. Welcome to ShareFile Support.

Our mission is to raise the bar for support in the tech industry. We're on your team. How can we help you?

GETTING STARTED WEB APPLICATION OUTLOOK PLUGIN

SYNC ENTERPRISE MASTER CLASS WEBINARS

More ways to get help — fast.

Type your question here

Ask the community.
Visit our [online support forum](#) to get help from other users and our support team and to report issues and give product feedback.

Send us your question.
[Submit your request here](#), and we'll get back to you as soon as we can.

Customer adoption training.
Need training now? [Check out our on-demand training library.](#)

Check system status.
Keep your finger on the pulse of all things ShareFile with real-time incident and status reports on our [system status page](#). Subscribe to updates [here](#).

What's new? Need help right away?

5. ALFRESCO (ANSES)

- <https://community.alfresco.com/welcome>

The screenshot shows the Alfresco Community website homepage. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Alfresco logo and links for Home, Alfresco Forums, Connect, Language Groups, Forum Help, and DevCon 2018. On the right side of the navigation bar, there are links for Log in, Register, and a search icon.

Below the navigation bar, there is an announcement banner: "ANNOUNCEMENT: Tech Talk Live TODAY and Office Hours on Friday! Show Details".

The main content area features a large green banner with the Alfresco logo and the text "Welcome to the Alfresco Community. Learn. Connect. Collaborate." with a "TAKE A TOUR" button.

On the right side of the main content area, there are three navigation buttons: "Forums", "Blogs", and "Wiki".

Below the main content area, there is a section for "ASK ALFRESCO COMMUNITY" with a search box and an "Ask it" button.

Below the "ASK ALFRESCO COMMUNITY" section, there is a section for "COMPANY & COMMUNITY NEWS".

The "COMPANY & COMMUNITY NEWS" section features a large image of a castle with the text "DEVCON 2018" overlaid. Below the image, there is a caption: "DevCon 2018: Registration Almost Full".

Below the caption, there is a paragraph: "Registration opened for DevCon on Wed, Nov 29th at 10am ET. We've decided to offer DevCon as a FREE event, so be sure to register soon, as we have less than 50 spots left".

Below the "COMPANY & COMMUNITY NEWS" section, there are three featured events:

- Dec 13: AWS Quickstart** (Tech Talk Live): A monthly, live session, devoted entirely to a technical topic related to Alfresco. In this session, we'll be joined by Mark Howarth and Martin Whittington, who will be discussing the AWS quickstart.
- Dec 15: To be announced ...** (Office Hours): Join us for another live session of Alfresco Office Hours, where you get to meet the people that create the Alfresco products, ask questions, and discuss their work. In this session, we'll be joined by Ole Hejskov and John Knowles.
- Watch a Video** (Alfresco ArchiTech Talks): Alfresco ArchiTech Talks are quick videos, intended to give you a technical overview of certain areas of focus for Alfresco. You can view the entire list here!

On the right side of the main content area, there are two sections:

- FEATURED EVENTS**:
 - Tech Talk Live #112: AWS Quickstart (Dec 13, 2017)
 - Office Hours (Dec 15, 2017)
 - Alfresco DevCon: Lisbon (Jan 16-18, 2018)
- NEWEST MEMBERS**:
 - voviak
 - jackonieuwenhuize
 - j.fintora
 - qyj0312
 - araúnasouzamaciel
 - lacroix-perrin_r

Project management platform inventory

#	Name of platform	web address	origin	free of charge (Y/N)	usable at program and JIP/JRP level (Y/N)	user friendly 1 (poor)-5(very)	easy structure 1 (poor)-5(very)	why do you like it
1	Confluence	https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/fpfis/wikis#all-updates	EU	N	y	4-5	4	nice user interface
2	Virtual Research Environments	https://www.d4science.org	CNR (IT)	could be	Y	4	4	it also provide computational resources, e.g. cloud computing with R-Studio. Has been developed under EU funding. Hosted by Italian research institute.
3	Open Science Framework	https://osf.io						
4	Sharefile							includes a version back up system, focuses on the secure sharing of files
5	ALFRESCO (ANSES)							
6	office 365		microsoft	N	project Y; program ?	2	?	not suitable for us

Open data management

Task 4.5

Why?

- Rules that beneficiaries have to follow in projects funded or co-funded under Horizon 2020.
 - **Build on previous research results**
 - **Encourage collaboration and avoid duplication of effort**
 - **Speed up innovation**
 - **Involve citizens and society**
- ⇒ Ensure access to publications and data is free of charge, and that data is preserved for the future.
- ⇒ Accounted for in the RfP of H2020 => => Grant Agreement

More ways

- You can find and understand your data when you need to use it
- Continuity if project staff leave or new researchers join
- Avoid unnecessary duplication e.g. re-collecting or re-working data
- Data sharing leads to more collaboration and advances research
- More visibility and greater impact to your research
- Others can cite your data so you gain credit

What is included?

- **Peer-reviewed scientific research articles**
 - (Also encouraged to make available monographs, books, conference proceedings, grey literature/reports)
- **Research data** (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data)
- **Open access = online access to scientific information**

Peer-reviewed scientific research articles

- **Self-archiving (" green open access)**
 - Deposition of article in repository in conjunction with, or after publication
 - Sometimes after an embargo period (up to 6 months)
- **Open access publishing (" gold open access)**
 - Immediately published in open access mode
 - APCs borne by the author's institution and/or funding body

NB:

- No obligation to publish, but if you publish it should be O.A...
- Can seek protection (e.g. patent) before publication

Research data

- Right to access and reuse digital research data
- Access = right to mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate openly accessible research data, free of charge

Open access: a two step process

- Deposit in repository (with metadata)
- Provide open access

R e s e a r c h

AS OPEN AS POSSIBLE, AS CLOSED AS NECESSARY

Grantees have the right to **opt-out**, but need to say **why**

Top three reasons for **opt-out**:

Data Management Plan

RESEARCH DATA - OPEN BY DEFAULT

Projects must have

Provides information on:

the data the research
will generate

how to ensure its
curation, preservation and
sustainability

what parts of that data
will be open (and how)

Contents of DMPs

1. Data Types, Formats, Standards and Capture Methods
2. Ethics and Intellectual Property
3. Access, Data Sharing and Reuse
4. Short-Term Storage and Data Management
5. Deposit and Long-Term Preservation
6. Resourcing

Overarching EJP Data Management Plan

First version by M6

Guidance

Individual project DMPs

Resources and guidance

- OpenAIRE
 - Repositories of repositories..re3data, OpenDOAR
- Digital Curation Centre
 - DMPOnline

DMPs are living documents – they will change

Logos

Logos

- Work in progress
- Project logos that are based on main logo
 - Certain customisation may be possible

Presentation of the 1st call projects (JRP and JIP)

One health surRveillance Initiative on harmOnization of data collection and interpretatiON (ORION)

Matthias Filter

Project Partner

MS	Organisation
BE	Veterinary and Agrochemical Research Centre (CODA-CERVA)
BE	Scientific Institute of Public Health (WIV-ISP)
DE	German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR)
DE	German Federal Research Institute for Animal Health (FLI)
DK	Technical University of Denmark Food (DTU)
DK	Statens Serum Institut (SSI)
NL	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research (WBVR)
NL	National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)
NO	Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH)
NO	Norwegian Veterinary Institute (NVI)
SE	Public Health Agency of Sweden (FoHM)
SE	Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA)
UK	Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)

Prototypic implementation of an integrated strategy for long-term consolidation and harmonization of One Health Surveillance (OHS) solutions => „OHS harmonization framework“

Implementation:

1. “OHS Surveillance Codex” (W1) **a high level guidance for harmonised, cross-sectional description and categorisation of surveillance data** covering all surveillance phases and all knowledge types.
2. “OHS Knowledge Hub” (W2) **a cross-domain inventory of public/veterinary health data sources as well as algorithms and tools** supporting OHS data generation, integration, analysis and interpretation. This includes an updateable inventory of OHS best practice solutions illustrating opportunities and challenges for European and national stakeholder.
3. “OHS Infrastructure Resources” – **technical and infrastructural resources that form the basis for successful harmonization and integration** of surveillance data and methods. These infrastructural resources include harmonized data standards, software libraries, ontologies, terminology mappings, software tools supporting the adoption of the “OHS Surveillance

Project Plan

Project Structure

Acknowledgement

Thanks to the ORION coordination team:

- Fernanda Dorea (SVA),
- Idesbald Boone & Taras Günther (BfR)

Thanks to all ORION project partners for their support during proposal generation

Thanks to EJP WP4, WP3, Support team

Thank you for your attention

Matthias Filter

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ONEHEALTH

COHESIVE: One Health Structure In Europe

Sweden:

SVA: National Veterinary Institute Sweden

PHA: Public Health Agency

NFA: National food Agency

Italy:

IZS AM: Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise

IZS LER: Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Lombardia e dell'Emilia-Romagna

ISS: Istituto Superiore di Sanita

Germany:

Bfr: The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment

FLI: Friedrich Loeffler Institute

United Kingdom:

APHA: Animal and Plant Health Agency

PHE: Public Health England

Belgium:

CODA-CERVA: Veterinary and Agrochemical Research Centre

WIV-ISP: The Scientific Institute of Public Health

Norway:

NIPH: Norwegian Institute of Public Health

NVI: Norwegian Veterinary Institute

Austria:

AGES: The Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety

Denmark:

DTU: Technical University of Denmark

The Netherlands:

RIVM: National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (coordinator)

WBVR: Wageningen Bioveterinary Research

ONEHEALTH

COHESIVE: Objectives

Stimulating One Health approaches at the national level within EU countries, focusing on strengthening human-veterinary collaboration with respect to early signaling and assessing zoonotic threats.

- Best practice methods -> design common procedures and tools
- Develop systematic ways
- Open workshops and local short term missions

Roadmap towards an EU zoonoses risk-assessment of risk-analysis structure.

- Existing risk analysis and epidemiological tools, skills and facilities
- Collaborate across country borders
- System analysis of detection of outbreaks, pilot between countries

ONEHEALTH

COHESIVE: Objectives

Collection and analysis of surveillance and outbreak data on (foodborne) zoonoses

- Provide IT tools and data -> outbreak situations & risk assessments
- Tracing, WGS and standardized risk assessments
- One, open source software platform
- Interoperable with the main data exchange systems

Capacity building within and between EU countries

- Improved collaboration between the human and veterinary domain
- At different levels
- Within and between countries -> networks of surveillance expertise
- Several pilots

COHESIVE – One Health Structure In Europe

ONEHEALTH

Identified collaborative partners/projects:

ORION

COMPARE

EFSA, ECDC

All EJP partners

Workshops also open for non-EJP partners

.....many more

EJP One Health, Joint Research Project, AMR-1

IMproving **P**henotypic **A**ntimicrobial **R**esistance **T**esting
Acronym: **IMPART**

Thirteen partners from nine countries involved:

- Anses (1), FR
- DTU (12), DK
- APHA (22), GB
- RIVM (32), NL
- NCOH (33.5), NL
- PIWet (37), PL
- IZSLT, IT (external partner)
- BfR (9), DE
- SSI (13), DK
- PHE (23), GB
- WR (33), NL
- NVI (35), NO
- SVA (44), SE

WP1 & WP2: optimizing detection of emerging AMR bacteria

- Goal **WP1**: selective isolation and detection of colistin resistant Enterobacteriaceae (mcr-positive isolates).
- Goal **WP2**: selective isolation and detection of carbapenemase resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CPE).
- Plan: review literature -> select strains-> organize pre-ring trial and ringtrial -> publish methods.

WP3: setting veterinary ECOFFs

- Goal: setting ECOFFs for veterinary antimicrobials supporting standardisation of AMR monitoring and accelerating determinacy of clinical breakpoints.
- Plan: prioritize antimicrobial/bug combinations -> fill EUCAST data base with collected/determined MICs-> set ECOFFs.

WP4: improving susceptibility testing of *Clostridium difficile*

- Goal: improving susceptibility testing of *C. difficile* by optimization disk diffusion
- Plan: collection of 500 isolates from humans, animals and food -> molecular typing of isolates -> optimize test conditions -> perform agar diffusion tests -> publish method with proposed ECOFFs

Integrative aspects of IMPART

- Our consortium stimulates partners from human health, animal health and food safety areas to fight AMR together by:
 - (1) harmonizing methods for isolation and detection of colistin and carbapenemase resistant bacteria,
 - (2) setting ECOFFs for veterinary antimicrobials,
 - (3) improving susceptibility testing of zoonotic bacteria (*C. difficile*).

*All generated knowledge will be disseminated according to the strategy described within **WP5!***

Animal &
Plant Health
Agency

Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics: the influence of geographic origin and management systems on resistance gene flows within humans, animals and the environment. -ARDIG

Lead: APHA

Partners: UoS; PHE; BfR; NVI; PI; UCM; ANSES; WUR; RKI

Reference to the Priority topic:

JRP, AMR2 – Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animal populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR.

Work Plan:

WP1: Comparison of AMR and antibiotic sales/usage data collected through existing national surveillance and research programs and assessment of risk factors.

WP2: Longitudinal studies of AMR persistence.

WP3: AMR characterization, transmission of plasmids and fitness of MDR isolates.

WP4: Project coordination and management.

Duration – 3 yrs; budget - € 3 000, 000

Graphical presentation of how each WP and Task fits together in this proposal.

A Gantt chart providing timeline for all tasks to undertaken in this proposal

Tasks		FIRST ANNUAL PERIOD				SECOND ANNUAL PERIOD				THIRD ANNUAL PERIOD			
		M1-3	M4-6	M7-9	M10-12	M13-15	M16-18	M19-21	M22-24	M25-27	M28-30	M31-33	M34-36
WP1	Task 1.1 - Exploration and collection of data available on AMR, AMU and potential risk factors	█	█	█	█								
	Task 1.2 - Investigation of trends, associations and risk factors					█	█	█	█				
	Task 1.3 - Develop recommendations for improved “One Health” surveillance strategies									█	█	█	█
WP2	Task 2.1: Assessment and selection of longitudinal data from historical studies	█	█	█	█								
	Task 2.2: Isolation of resistant Enterobacteriaceae on farms	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█				
	Task 2.3: Isolation of resistant Enterobacteriaceae in hospitals and care facilities	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█				
	Task 2.4: Data analysis of collected resistant Enterobacteriaceae on national levels								█	█	█	█	
	Task 2.5: Comparative analysis of collected isolates on a Europe-wide level										█	█	█
WP3	Task 3.1: Detailed molecular characterisation of AMR genes present in human, animal, food and environment isolates from WP1 and WP2.	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█				
	Task 3.2: Characterisation of prevalent circulating plasmids and their transfer <i>in vitro</i>				█	█	█	█	█				
	Task 3.3: Fitness cost of AMR and stability of plasmids in different host strain background				█	█	█	█	█		█	█	█
	Task 3.4: Measuring AMR plasmid dissemination <i>in vivo</i> in mouse and <i>Galleria</i> , and chicken and pig <i>in-vitro</i> gut models								█	█	█	█	█
WP4	Task 4.1: Steering committee quarterly meeting	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
	Task 4.2: Consortium members annual meeting	█			█				█			█	
	Task 4.3: Reporting and communication				█				█			█	

Integrative aspect of the project

- This proposal brings together leading experts working on AMR from veterinary, environment and human sectors based in ten institutes, in five Member States and one non-member state, all playing key roles in AMR research .
- It provides an unique opportunity to study the distribution and stability of mobile genetic elements, the impact of their transmission and selection across different sectors and regions of EU.
- The project aims to substantially improve comparability of data from different sectors (animals, food, humans) concerning antimicrobial usage and AMR.
- The scientific outputs from this project will help provide a better understanding of the drivers of AMR transmission and its consequence across these regions, which may be studied more widely in future.

National Institute for Public Health
and the Environment
Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport

The consortium

National Institute for Public Health and the
Environment (RIVM), The Netherlands
(Eelco Franz, coordinator)

Danish Technical University (DTU), Denmark
(Tine Hald, deputy coordinator)

Wageningen Bioveterinary Research (WBVR), The
Netherlands

Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung (BfR), Germany

Animal Plant Health Protection Agency (APHA),
United Kingdom

French Agency for Food, Environmental and
Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES), France

Istituto Superiore di Sanita (ISS), Italy

Norwegian veterinary Institute (NVI), Norway

*Univeristy Medical Centre Utrecht (UMCU), The
Netherlands*

RaDAR (JRP)

Risk and Disease Burden of
Antimicrobial Resistance

Project background & goals

- Antimicrobial resistance threatens the effective prevention and treatment of an increasing range of infections
- Containment of AMR Requires improvement of AMR **attribution**, **risk assessment** and **disease burden**
- Hindered by complexity, knowledge gaps, different approaches, diversity in data and data sources

(epidemiological, microbiological, molecular)

Project background & goals

The key objective of this proposal is to systematically integrate data from diverse modalities (*) to obtain consensus estimates for attribution, risk (factors), and disease burden. Subsequently, this will be used for determining the most effective strategies for controlling transmission and to mitigate risk.

1. Bioinformatics tools (metagenomics) and retrieve relevant information
2. Models regarding AMR development, transmission & spread
3. Machine learning approaches for risk assessment
4. Disease burden outcome trees and structured expert judgement (gaps)
5. (Bayesian) evidence synthesis of all available data and information for consensus estimates on source attribution, risks of exposure and burden

In control...

Despite being data-intensive and logistically demanding, the current project is highly feasible

- Only use of data already available which minimizes financial risk
- The consortium ensures broad access to expertise and data
- The consortium has a history of collaboration
- The consortium represents institutes with high quality standards and facilities, providing a suitable work environment.
- The planned research activities do not raise specific ethical issues

Intergration

The institutions involved will learn how to collaborate on the complex issue of AMR ultimately applying these techniques for best results across Europe

- Workshops to discuss the flow and sharing of data and information across disciplines involved in the project
- Sharing and harmonization of best-practices and specific aspects (software, scripts, data entering processes, etc.).
- Close collaboration with other EJP projects
- Training of new experts

The people make the succes...

Tine Hald, Aline de Koeijer, Martin Bootsma, Thomas Sellhorst, Christine Muller-Graf, Annemarie Kaesbohrer, Lucas Busani, Annalisa Pantosti, Robin Simons, Emma Snary, Madelaine Norstrom, Camilla Sekse, Michel-Yves Mistou, Pascal Sanders, Sophie Granier, Engeline van Duijkeren, Eric Evers, Axel Bonacic, Scott McDonald, Lapo Mughini Gras & Eelco Franz

METAGENOMIC ARRAY DETECTION OF EMERGING VIRUS IN EU (MAD-VIR)

Anders Fomsgaard, AFO@SSI.dk

Statens Serum Institut, Denmark

Microarray
technology transfer

Sample shipment

GANTT DIAGRAM

WP		1 st annual period						2 nd annual period					
		1-2	3-4	5-6	7-8	9-10	11-12	13-14	15-16	17-18	19-20	21-22	23-24
1	Coordination and management												
2	Sample collection												
3	3.1 Technology trans												
	3.2 QA-validation												
	3.3 Sample analysis												
4	Data sharing												

European Joint programme One Health

TOX-Detect project

Mirjana Andjelkovic, WIV-ISP

Pre kick off meeting – December 15th, 2017, Brussels

Background

➤ Involvement of bacterial toxins in food-borne outbreaks occurred in EU

Distribution of food-borne and waterborne outbreaks per causative agent in the EU Member States, 2015

Increase of 7 % of food-borne due to bacterial toxins during the last 5 years

Background

➤ Involvement of bacterial toxins in food-borne outbreaks occurred in EU

Number of	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. cereus</i>	<i>Clostridium</i> (including <i>Cl. perfringens</i> , <i>botulinum</i> ...)
Outbreaks	434 (39 S + 395 W)	291 (24 S + 267 W)	124 (39 S + 85 W)
Cases (ills)	3630 (758 S + 2872 W)	3131 (518 S + 2613 W)	2086 (752 S + 1334 W)
Hospitalisations	316 (113 S + 178203 W)	101 (25 S + 76 W)	80 (39 S + 41 W)
Deaths	0	0	3

- 52 % of food-borne outbreaks (FBO) due to *S. aureus*
- 12% of FBO classified as strong evidence
 ➔ need of tools for detection of toxins in foods involved in FBO

European Joint Programme One Health TOX-Detect

TOX-detect: Development and harmonization of innovative methods for comprehensive analysis of food-borne toxigenic bacteria, ie. Staphylococci, Bacillus cereus and Clostridium perfringens

- **Context:** develop tools to fully characterize FBO due to bacteria producing toxins
- **Various FBOs remain under « weak evidence » status as bacteria and/or toxins can not be detected in food remnants**
- **Tool box strategy to improve characterization of bacteria and/or toxins**

European Joint Programme One Health TOX-Detect

- **Duration: 3 years (01/2018 → 12/2020)**
- **Context:** Call H2020 One Health – European Joint Program: Emerging threats: Development and harmonization of non-NGS-based methods for detection and tracing of food borne zoonose agents, emerging threats and antimicrobial resistance determinants
- **Coordination: Anses (Staphylococci, Bacillus and Clostridium Unit)**
- **Partners: n=6**

- **Budget: 2.8 M€**

Partners

P1: Anses (France)

Food safety laboratory, Staphylococci, Bacillus and Clostridium Unit (J-A Hennekinne)
Fougères laboratory, Toxicology of contaminants unit (V. Fessard)
Nancy Hydro Laboratory, platform of MALDI-ToF (B. Gassilloud)

P4: WIV-ISP (Belgium)

Chemical Residues and Contaminants group (M. Andjelkovic);
Foodborne Pathogens- toxins and food poisoning group (S. Denayer)

P9: BfR (Germany)

Microbial Toxins (A. Fetsch)

P18: INRA (France)

MICALIS-PIMS (N. Rama Rao)
MICALIS-GME (M. Gohar)
UR454 & Plate-Forme d'Exploration du Métabolisme composante protéomique (M. Hébraud)

P19: Institut Pasteur (France)

Structural Mass Spectrometry and Proteomics Unit (J. Chamot-Rooke)
Collection of Institut Pasteur (D. Clermont, C. Bizet)
French National reference center for anaerobic bacteria and botulism (C. Mazuet)

P33: NVI (Norway)

Department of Bacteriology - Food and GMO (T. Skjerdal)

Main objectives

- Establishment of an EU-wide network focusing on the detection and identification of *S. aureus*, *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*,
- Evaluation of different diagnostic approaches (e.g. spectrometric, immunological, functional approaches) to characterize *S. aureus*, *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*,
- Generation and characterization of a reference collection of bacterial strains,
- Implementation and development of methods to identify bacteria and associated toxins and/or virulence factors,
- Transfer of the developed methods through Proficiency Test organization

EJP OH TOX-Detect: Work packages & leaders

WP0: Anses

WP3: WIV-ISP

WP6: Anses, INRA

WP1: Pasteur

WP4: BfR, INRA

WP2: INRA, Anses

WP5: Anses

EJP OH TOX-Detect: Gantt

TOX-Detect	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3			
	M1-3	M4-6	M7-9	M10-12	M13-15	M16-18	M19-21	M22-24	M25-27	M28-30	M31-33	M34-36
Coordination Collections	WP 0	D0.1				D0.2	D0.3			D0.4		D0.5-0.6
	WP 1											
	T.1.1	D1.1										
	T.1.2	D1.1										
	T.1.3	D1.1										
Virulence factors	T.1.4	D1.2										
	WP 2											
	T.2.1							D2.1				
	T.2.2							D2.2				
	T.2.3									D2.3		
Mass Spectrometry	WP 3											
	T.3.1								D3.1			
	T.3.2								D3.2			
	T.3.3								D3.3			
	T.3.4									D3.4		
Immunological tools	WP 4											
	T.4.1											
	T.4.2											
	T.4.3										D4.1	
Interlaboratory trials	WP 5											
	T.5.1								D5.1			D5.2
	T.5.2											D5.2
	T.5.3											D5.2
Dissemination	WP6											D6.1 6.2

Face-to-face meeting

NOVA

Jenny Frössling, SVA, Sweden

Pre-kick-off EJP One Health
Brussels, Dec 15, 2017

Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost-effective surveillance across the food chain

WP1 leader	<i>BE</i>	CODA
	<i>DE</i>	BfR
	<i>DE</i>	FLI
	<i>DE</i>	RKI
WP5 leader	<i>DK</i>	DTU
Deputy coordinator, WP2 leader	<i>DK</i>	SSI
WP4 leader	<i>ES</i>	INIA
	<i>ES</i>	UCM
WP3 leader	<i>FR</i>	ANSES
	<i>FR</i>	InVS/SpF
	<i>UK</i>	APHA
	<i>UK</i>	PHE
	<i>IT</i>	ISS
	<i>IT</i>	IZS
	<i>NL</i>	RIVM
	<i>NO</i>	NIPH
	<i>NO</i>	NVI
Coordinator, WP0 leader	<i>SE</i>	SVA
	<i>SE</i>	PHAS

Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost-effective surveillance across the food chain

- We need to make sure we use our resources in the best way
- NOVA will develop and test methods to assess surveillance performance

Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost-effective surveillance across the food chain

- We cannot afford not to use all the relevant information out there
- NOVA will explore ways to capture new data sources

Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost-effective surveillance across the food chain

INTEGRATIVE ASPECTS

- Aim to include all parts of the food chain
- Partners are a mix of Med and Vet institutes
- Includes partners across Europe
 - Sharing knowledge and methods
- Connection to the EJP integrative projects
- Plan to integrate new methods in our everyday work and improve our ability to support decision makers

European Joint programme - One Health

LISTADAPT project

Adaptive traits of *Listeria monocytogenes* to its
diverse ecological niches

Laurent GUILLIER

ANSES Food safety laboratory

Pre kick off meeting – December 15th, 2017, Brussels

Partners

P1: Anses (France)

Food safety laboratory, Salmonella Listeria Unit (L. Guillier)
Fougères laboratory, (C. Soumet, A. Bridier)
Ploufragan laboratory NGS platform (Y. Blanchard)

P2: AGES (Austria)

RL for *L. monocytogenes* (A. Pietzka)

P8: VRI (Czech republic)

NRL for *L. monocytogenes* (R. Karpiskova)

P12: DTU (Denmark)

Research Group for Genomic Epidemiology (R. Hendriksen)

P18: INRA (France)

INRA Dijon UMR 1347 Agroecology (P. Piveteau)
INRA Clermont UR454 & Plate-Forme Protoemoc (M. Hébraud, M. Deveaux)

P28: IZS AM (Italy)

NRL for *L. monocytogenes* (F. Pomilio, C. Camma)

Veterinærinstituttet
National Veterinary Institute

P33: NVI (Norway)

Department of Bacteriology - Food and GMO (T. Skjerdal, K. Lagesen, L. Nesse)

P36: NFA (Sweden)

NRL for *L. monocytogenes* (S. Thisted-Lambertz)

Background of LISTADAPT

- *Listeria monocytogenes*:

Ubiquitous saprophyte facultative intracell. pathogen

- Still a problem for public health:

EFSA's opinion of the increase incidence of listeriosis at EU-level
(EFSA 2017)

- WGS

A lot is done on virulence... far less investigation on adaptation in environment, farm, industry

4 objectives of LISTADAPT

1. Decipher genetic traits linked to adaptation in various ecological niches

2. Generate a database of 4000 genomes (mainly farms environment, ...)

3. Develop and implement cutting-edge methodologies (new phenotypic analysis, GWAS)

4. Make available common resources for European research

WPs of LISTADAPT

- **WP1 : Strain collection** (existing strains + new sampling)
 - Animal
 - Country
 - Environment, farm, industry

- **WP2 : Sequencing**

WPs of LISTADAPT

- WP3: Phenotypic characterization

- Biocides
- Adhesion and biofilm formation
- Survival and persistence in soil microcosm

- WP4: Identification of genetic traits

GWAS (snp, kmers, genes)

- Niches
- Phenotypes

Integrative aspects of LISTADAPT

- Environment – Animal – Food

- Reference activities – Research activities

- Phenotype – genotype

- Sharing data and methodologies

FBZ2-METASTAVA

Standardisation and **va**lidity of **meta**genomic methods for the detection of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats.

- Veterinary and Agrochemical Research Center **CODA-CERVA**, BE
 - Steven Van Borm^{CO, WP4, WP5}, Frank Vandebussche
 - Kris De Clercq, Andy Haegeman
- Scientific Institute for Public Health **WIV-ISP**, BE
 - Nancy Roosens, Sigrid De Keersmaecker^{WP2}, Kevin Vanneste
 - Steven Van Gucht, Vanessa Suin
 - Sarah Denayer
- Friedrich Loeffler Institut **FLI**, Inst. Of Diagnostic Virology, DE
 - Martin Beer, Anne Pohlmann, Dirk Höper^{WP1}
- Swedish National Veterinary Institute **SVA**, SE
 - Lihong Liu, Mikhayil Hakhverdyan
- Netherlands Centre for One Health **NCOH**, ErasmusMC, NL
 - Marion Koopmans, Matthew Cotten
- French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety **ANSES**, FR
 - Yannick Blanchard^{WP3}, Nicole Pavio, Sandra Martin-Latil, Isabelle Kempf

CODA - CERVA

Background & scope

- NGS → untargeted massive parallel sequencing
 - Hypothesis free sequencing
 - Identification, characterisation
 - Multiple infection, unexpected or new species or variants
- Ongoing efforts: tool development for metagenomic data generation and analysis
 - COMPARE, EFFORT, GMI
- METASTAVA: bring metagenomics closer to diagnostic laboratories
 - Validation, quality assurance, reference data

CODA - CERVA

Project organisation

Work plan

- WP1: reference data, method selection, informed metagenomic workflow design.
 - ← other projects (WP4), literature, in house and public datasets.
- WP2: Quality assurance tools for validation & interpretation
 - Quality metrics. ← norms, mining ref datasets
 - External (exogenous) control for metagenomics
 - Reproducibility & batch effects
 - Proficiency test
 - Application to parallel projects & existing datasets
- WP3: Evaluation of analytical properties (S_n , S_p) of metagenomics
 - Hepatitis E virus (pig sausage, human serum, animal fecal material)
 - Norovirus (fruit, fecal & vomit)
 - DNA viruses (e.g. cowpox virus) (swabs, skin lesions)
 - Shiga toxin/verotoxin-producing Escherichia coli STEC/VTEC (food samples)
 - Detecting AMR resistance genes in diagnostic samples (pig feces)

Integration

WP4 coordination
with related
projects &
Dissemination

- 6 public health institutes. Implement and translate new technologies in public diagnostic infrastructure.
- Synergy with ongoing efforts : WP1 & WP4
- Coordination with other efforts and projects: WP4
 - COMPARE (H2020).
Infrastructures and analytical workflows for NGS based clinical, public health and research studies
 - EFFORT (FP7)
AMR focus including metagenomics in AMR surveillance
 - GMI
Global network for nucleic acid based infectious disease identification and characterisation
 - ISO Working groups
ISO TC34/SC9/WG25 WGS for typing and genomic characterisation

CODA - CERVA

Air sampling:

A Low-Cost Screening Tool in Biosecured Broiler Production

Acronym: **AIR SAMPLE**
EU funding: **Approx. 1 mill. Euro**
Period: **2 years (Jan 2018 - Dec. 2019).**
Coordinator: **Jeffrey Hoorfar, DTU Food.**

Partners:

Julia Christensen & Jeffrey Hoorfar, DTU Food.
Gro Johannessen, Mona Torp & Camilla Sekse, NVI.
Renáta Karpíšková & Ivana Koláčková, VRI.
Kinga Wieczorek & Jacek Osek, NVRI.
Elisabetta Di Giannatale & Giuliano Garofolo, IZSAM.

Copenhagen, Denmark.
Oslo, Norway.
Brno, Czech Republic.
Pulawy, Poland.
Teramo, Italy.

Pre-slaughter sampling

7-10 days before slaughter

Current method, boot swabs

Future method, air sampling

- Campylobacter not detected in boot swabs.

AIR SAMPLE

Task 1.1 Creates a sample bank (air boot-swab samples) from different regions

Task 1.2 Develops of a non-complex DNA extraction protocol for qPCR or diagnostic metagenomics of gelatin-filter samples

Task 2.1 Focuses on validation of air sampling and DNA extraction methods

Task 2.2 Will promote the outcomes of the project to relevant stakeholders

Experimental setup

Air samples

Boot swabs

Enrichment qPCR

Diagnostic Metagenomics

Enrichment broth

Selective plates

Colony PCR

Integrative activities

- A shared sample bank.
- A harmonized air-sampling protocol.
- PhD studies.
- Exchange of scientists and technologies.
- Uptake of the method by other EJP partners.
- A Successful industry and regulatory workshop.
- Acceptance of the air sampling method by European regulators.

MOMIR-PPC

Monitoring the gut microbiota and immune response to predict, prevent and control zoonoses in humans and livestock in order to minimize the use of antimicrobials.

Philippe Velge: INRA

Martine Denis: ANSES

Ivan Rychlik: VRI

Mikael Lenz Strube: DTU-VET

Antonio Rodríguez Bertos: VIVASET-UCM

Roberto La Ragione: Univ. Surrey

Paolo Pasquali: ISS

Giovanni Alborali: IZSLER

Thomas Hagenaars: CVI/DLO

Anke Stüken : NIPH/FHI

Mart de Jong: NCOH

~~Anastas Pashov: SAIM~~

BACKGROUND

- Asymptomatic carrier animals are a serious food safety and health issue
- Host heterogeneity in infection
 - The Super-shedders are responsible for the majority of the infections
-
-
- **BUT**
- The majority of the control measures are based on homogeneity of host infection
- What distinguishes super-shedders from other infected hosts?
- Why some hosts are super-shedders?

OBJECTIVES

- Development of new approaches to predict, prevent, identify and control the appearance of animal and human Super-shedders based on immune response and modulation of gut microbiota composition
- Development of new mathematical models of pathogen transmission within a population (heterogeneity of infection ; role of gut microbiota)
- Development of new intervention strategies to:
 - Optimize husbandry and feeding practices,
 - Decrease the use of antimicrobials and mitigate the spread of antimicrobials resistance genes

High efficiency and partnership,
one model: *Salmonella* excretion in chicken, pig and human

PROGRAM

Workpackages

1- Risk prediction: **P22**, Roberto La Ragione

- Predictive immunological markers
- Predictive microbiota markers
- Risk factors of human persistence
- Virulence of *Salmonella* strains

2- Prevention of the appearance of Super-shedders: **P16**, Antonio Rodríguez Bertos

- Use of probiotics
- Use of pre-biotics and nutraceutical

3- Modelling the transmission: **P30**, Thomas Hagenaars

- Transmission modelling at within-host and between-host scales
- Intervention strategies: Identification and evaluation tools

4- Communication and Dissemination for Impact: **P18**-Tours, Philippe Velge

- Dissemination of data within the project
- Dissemination of data outside the project

INTEGRATIVE ASPECT

- This project gathers biologists working on human, pig and poultry and mathematicians to better understand zoonotic infection and develop mathematical models of pathogen transmission
- To define **achievable objectives** and to develop **partnerships** between the institutes: **focus on heterogeneity of infection/excretion of *Salmonella***
- Aims: Development of predictive biomarkers and improvement of preventive and control measures of foodborne zoonoses
 - **Detect the most susceptible host**
 - **Counterbalance this susceptibility by modulating** immune parameters
gut microbiota composition
Biosecurity measures

MedVetKlebs

***Klebsiella pneumoniae* from ecology to source attribution and transmission control**

Sylvain Brisse

Biodiversity and Epidemiology of Bacterial Pathogens
Institut Pasteur, Paris, France

Klebsiella pneumoniae

Community pathogen

- Friedländer's pneumonia; pyogenic liver abscess
- Hypervirulent *K. pneumoniae* (HVKP)

Nosocomial pathogen

- Urinary, respiratory, blood infections, ...
- Outbreaks
- **ESK**APE: multidrug resistance pioneer

Ubiquitous

- Human and animal carriage plants, water, soil, ...
- Animal infections

Klebsiella pneumoniae resistance

Combined Resistance to 3GC, quinolones & aminoglycoside, invasive isolates, 2014

Carbapenem-R KP

Non-visible countries

Klebsiella pneumoniae: carriage precedes disease

Montgomerie 1979
Martin *et al.* 2016
Gorrie *et al.* BioRxiv 2017

- Infection by endogenous strain
- Nosocomial outbreaks

- Critical knowledge gaps
- Infection control barriers

MedVetKlebs

WP1. Detection & isolation methods

WP2. Broad sampling of potential reservoirs & sources

WP3. Population genomics, gene flux & modeling

WP4. Management & dissemination

Med-Vet *Klebsiella* project (2017-2019)

#	Applicant Name	Short name	PI	Country
1	Institut Pasteur	IP	Sylvain Brisse	FR
2	National Institute for Agronomical Research	INRA	Pascal Piveteau	FR
3	French Agency for Food, Env. and Occupational Health Safety	ANSES	Jean-Yves Madec	FR
4	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Security	AGES	Franz Allerberger	AT
5	Statens Serum Institute	SSI	Carsten Struve	DK
6	Technical University of Denmark	DTU	Sara Pires	DK
7	University College Dublin	UCD	Shea Fanning	IE
8	Veterinary Institute Teramo	IZSAM	Francesco Pomilio	IT
9	Netherlands Center for One Health	NCOH	Willem van Schaik	NL
10	National University of Ireland Galway	NUIG	Dearbhaile Morris	IE

Next steps & questions

- Let's get started!

Second call

Two rounds of calls

2016	2017 Submission & selection	2018 – 2019	2020 - 2021 - 2022
		Start of first round of Research & Integrative Projects	Start of second round of Research & Integrative Projects
WP2: Strategy Research Agenda (v1) Identification of teams		11 Research Projects 2 Integrative Projects	
		WP2: Strategy Research Agenda (v2) Identification of teams	10 Research Projects 3 Integrative Projects

The procedures for 2nd call will aim to broaden the network geographically, and in terms of topics and Med-Vet collaboration/contribution